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AGROSERV ACCESS POLICY

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General information

Project name	AgroServ Integrated services supporting a sustainable agroecological transition
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Work package	WP1
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Project coordinator	Michel Boër michel.boer@anaee.eu
Dissemination level	Public
Main author	Michel Boër
Date of approval	
Approved by	
Submission date	

Version history

Version n°	Date	Description
V1.0		Initial version
V2.0	12/01/2024	Consistency of terms, definitions revised, typos

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Agroserv Access Policy

Definitions

Research Infrastructure (RI): Facilities that provide resources and services for the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields. This definition includes the associated human resources, and it covers major equipment or sets of instruments; knowledge related facilities such as collections, archives or scientific data infrastructures; computing systems, communication networks, and any other infrastructure, of a unique nature and open to external users, essential to achieve excellence in research and innovation. Where relevant, they may be used beyond research, for example for education or public services, and they may be 'single-sited', 'virtual' or 'distributed' (from the EU Grant Agreement)¹

ERIC: European Research Infrastructure Consortium under EU regulation 723/2009

Unit of Access (UA): For a given installation, the unit by which access by the user is accounted for.

User or User group (user): The external committer of resources that exploits the transnational or virtual access services offered by the AgroServ project; the user can be an individual or a team of researchers from the public or private sector.

Access Manager (AM): The main contact for users and manager of the access provision at the level of the Research Infrastructure. The AM provide information to the users and redirect them to the appropriate *installation* (see below) of her/his RI.

Installation: under the AgroServ project, an installation is the elementary facility, that belongs to a RI, where all or part of the transnational access is effectively provided in form of one or more services.

Installation Manager (IM): the person, or group of persons, in charge of the management of the installation, and in contact with the users for this specific installation.

Access

Access to the research infrastructures under the project AgroServ is provided free of charge to the **User** once their proposals for the use of services have been approved and passed the eligibility criteria, and the feasibility and scientific evaluations during the selection phases. The **User** must follow the access request submission procedure as defined in the call for proposals and the guidelines that are available on the AgroServ web site.

Access is provided within the scope of the project, for research pertaining to "sustainable and resilient agriculture and agroecological transitions". The access to services requires that the applications, for research or non-research objectives, should be interdisciplinary or transdisciplinary in nature, and the User must access several **RIs** within the Consortium, during the lifetime of their project.

Trans-national access

In accordance with the AgroServ Grant Agreement with the European, the majority of the members of the **User group** must work in a country other than the country of the selected installation(s) offering the

¹ For more information the reader is referred to the glossary in the [EU portal](#).

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TA/VA is(are) located, unless the access is provided by an **ERIC** or a similar legal entity. In AgroServ this applies to **Access** provided by the AnaEE-ERIC, EMBRC-ERIC, EuroBioimaging ERIC, ELIXIR, and Lifewatch-ERIC.

Access for a **User group** with a majority of members not working in an EU member state, or in Horizon Europe associated countries, is limited to 20% of the total amount of **unit of access** provided under the grant.

Procedure and criteria for selecting a proposal and User / User group

The User / User group must submit a request according to the procedure described in the Guidelines (D1.2) and in the text of the AgroServ open call for TA/VA.

The proposal submitted by the **User group** will be evaluated by a Proposal Review Committee (PRC), which will be composed of international experts in the field of agroecology. At least half of them will be independent of the Consortium. The PRC will submit a short-list of User groups based on scientific merit. Prior to evaluation by the PRC, the feasibility will be assessed internally by the installations to which the User group has requested Access. The corresponding feedback/report will be made available to the PRC.

The proposal should be compliant with the User guidelines, the text of the call, and the general objective of the AgroServ proposal.

Modality of access

Physical or remote access to the installations will be made according to the specific procedures of the selected installations, and following the schedule which will have been agreed upon between the User group and the manager of the installation. A written agreement between the User and the access providers will delineate the action to be undertaken, the period of use, the details of the stay(s) of the users, and the obligations of both parties.

Data management

The user will provide a data management plan (DMP) which is compliant with the DMP of the project, available on the web site of AgroServ, as well as with the DMP of the access providers.

Ethics

The user will comply with the Ethics rules and guidelines of the AgroServ project, available on the web site of the project, and to the specific rules of the access providers.

General obligations of the user / user group

At the end of the Access provision, the user/user group will submit a report which will describe the technical and preliminary scientific project outcomes, and any other information relevant to the Access. This report will be sent within 30 days after the last date of access. In the case of access lasting more than one year, the user will submit an intermediate report within 30 days after the first period of 1 year, and each consecutive year. Either a form, or online submission module, will be made available to the user. In addition, the user will be requested to provide feedback about the TNA from which they benefited.

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The User explicitly agrees that the data acquired within the framework of the project will be made publicly available after a period of 6 months after the end of the access period at all installations. A longer period may be exceptionally agreed on sound scientific, technical, or IPR reasons, by the executive board of the AgroServ project, provided this has been explicitly stated in the proposal, following advice from the PRC, and in accordance with the Grant Agreement, Consortium agreement, and overall EU rules.

Users are expected to publish their results within a reasonable time in the open-access literature or in any appropriate open-access repository. The User will inform the project, even after the end of the grant period in 2028, about all publications that exploited data and information acquired from Access to the facilities under the AgroServ project, and whenever relevant the DOI for data. Publications will be in open-access journals, or the PDF of the accepted article be available in an open repository.

Acknowledgement

In all publications and presentations, the user will acknowledge the support from the EU and from the AgroServ project. In all public material, the user will add the Horizon Europe and AgroServ logos available on the project web site. In all publications and dissemination actions including poster presentations, the user will add the following acknowledgement: “The research leading to these results has received funding from the AgroServ project, under the European Union Horizon Europe research and innovation programme.”

A copy of all publications and printed material will be sent to the project.

Press releases should be submitted to the project in advance for approval. The project coordinator will inform the User within 10 working days on their accord for the press release, on the modifications, and on a possible common press release with the project or partners of the project.

Guidelines

The user is referred to the text of the calls issued by AgroServ, which will be published on the website by June 2023, and to the guidelines for access for further details on access). The AgroServ calls will be published on the project web site.